

Islamic cultural acculturation in the saeyyang pattuqduq tradition in karama village, tinambung sub district, Polewali Mandar District

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Abstract:

This research uses a qualitative approach with field research, integrating historical, anthropological, and religious approaches. The sources of data for this research involved the Karama Village Head, Karama Village culturists, Karama Village religious leaders, and Karama Village Village Head. The data collection methods include observation, interviews, photovoice, and documentation. The data analysis was carried out through three stages: data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing. The results showed that acculturation in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition involves elements of local culture such as Mandarese language, music, and traditional clothing influenced by Islamic teachings. This process occurs through an inclusive cultural approach, fostering unity and harmony, and respect for customs, which preachers and ulama carry out in harmonising local cultural elements with Islamic teachings. Islamization is evident in the changes in prayer readings, ritual implementation, and the orientation of the purpose of the activity, which was originally magical, turning into a thanksgiving ritual based on faith in Allah SWT. The implications of this research are expected to provide insight into the form of acculturation in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition in Karama Village, as well as enrich understanding of the dynamics of the relationship between local culture and Islam in the local community.

Keywords: Cultural Acculturation, Saeyyang Pattuqduq, Mandar.

INTRODUCTION

This research focuses on the phenomenon of Islamic cultural acculturation in local cultural traditions in West Sulawesi Province, especially in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition in Karama Village, Tinambung District, Polewali Mandar Regency. West Sulawesi Province, which was officially formed in 2005, is a region rich with diverse ethnicities, cultures, and traditions that involve interactions between local cultures and the influence of Islam. One interesting cultural aspect to be studied is the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition, a form of acculturation between Mandar culture and Islam.

The acculturation process arises when a human group with a particular culture faces different elements of foreign culture, so that elements of foreign culture are gradually accepted and processed into their own culture, without causing the loss of their cultural personality. From this, it can be seen that acculturation is the acceptance of foreign cultural elements, which are combined with the old culture so that there is a mixture of both parties, but still within the limits of not leaving the authenticity of the old culture. The existence of acculturation results in the birth of a new idea with two different but interrelated elements.

Acculturation refers to cultural and psychological changes due to encounters with people of other cultures who exhibit different behaviours. Culture can affect the diversity in Indonesia, as discussed in the author's discussion, namely regarding the relationship between culture and religion. Culture and religion often influence each other, and of course, they can influence each other; either complement each other, or there is reciprocity between the two, as with religion. Religion is a belief system that contains teachings and guidance for its adherents to be saved from hellfire, namely life after death, so that religion is a means for humans to conduct relationships/communication from one religion to another (Syahit Achmad & Daulay Zainudin, 2003).

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A legacy from ancestors is still passed down from generation to generation. One of the cultures in the area is influenced by Islam, namely the Saeyyang Pattuqduq culture in the Mandar Tribe, precisely in West Sulawesi Province, Tinambung District, Polewali Mandar Regency.

Knowing history is knowing the nation. Moreover, knowing Mandar's history means knowing Mandar. The definition or meaning of Mandar is still confusing. Mandar comes from a word that is still alive and used until now, namely mandar, same as Manda', which means strong (Syah, 2008).

Culture is a process of adaptation because some argue that the conception of culture is an adaptation to the environment. Meanwhile, cultural diversity is caused by the environment (environmental determinism). Although this view is not entirely correct, until now, there is an assessment that one of the causes of cultural diversity is also caused by ecological factors (possiblism), in areas where the culture is maintained and remains thick, such as the culture in the villages.

Indonesian culture has extraordinary wealth in various aspects, such as language, religion, art, and customs (Mutia Mutia, 2018). This culture is passed down from generation to generation and continues to develop through social and environmental dynamics. One form of influence that is interesting to study is how the teachings of Islam can interact and adapt existing local traditions. This creates the phenomenon of acculturation (Murniasih Anak Agung Ayu, 2016) which enriches Indonesian culture, but it still maintains its local characteristics.

In this context, the meeting between Islamic and Mandarin cultures resulted in unique traditions, including the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition. This tradition has strong roots in local culture, but along with the spread of Islam, it developed into part of Islamic religious rituals, especially those related to the Qur'an. This acculturation process gave birth to a tradition that has religious values while involving elements of local culture, such as the use of horses that symbolize the tradition.

Saeyyang Pattuqduq has a deep meaning for the Mandar people. This tradition contains moral and spiritual messages encouraging children to learn Islam and memorize the Qur'an more actively. In this tradition, children who have completed the memorization of the Qur'an will be paraded around the village on a horse called "Saeyyang Pattuqduq" (dancing horse) (Alimuddin Muhammad Ridwan, 2011). This process is not only a symbol of the child's success in memorizing the Qur'an, but also as a form of respect for tradition and their ancestors, so that the performance of the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition is a motivation for a child to be more active in reciting the Koran and be able to memorize the Qur'an (Wirdanengsih, 2009).

It is also explained in the Word of Allah QS. Yunus / 10: 58, which reads:

قُلْ بِفَضْلِ اللَّهِ وَبِرَحْمَتِهِ فَبِذَلِكَ فَلْيَفْرَحُوا هُوَ خَيْرٌ مِمَّا يَجْمَعُونَ

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58. Say (Prophet Muhammad), "By the bounty of Allah and His mercy, let them rejoice. It is better than what they have gathered" (Ministry of Religious Affairs, 2015).

Therefore, the acculturation in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition shows how important it is to balance preserving local culture and religious teachings. As seen in the use of horses in this tradition, existing local culture is not lost in acculturation with Islam, but is maintained and combined with new religious elements. For example, the unique way the Qur'an is recited gives the tradition a distinctive character that distinguishes it from Qur'an recitations commonly found in other regions.

This research aims to understand more deeply the acculturation of Islamic culture in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition in Tinambung District, Polewali Mandar Regency. This process will also explain how this tradition develops and is accepted by the community and how it plays a role in enriching local cultural identity.

This study is hoped to contribute to the preservation of Mandar cultural traditions and add insight into the dynamics of cultural acculturation in Indonesia, especially in the context of interactions between Islam and local culture. Thus, the cultural diversity in Indonesia, especially in West Sulawesi, can continue to be maintained and appreciated as an essential part of the nation's cultural wealth.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses the Field Research method or qualitative research to gain deeper insight into the topic under study. Qualitative research can be done with various approaches, such as narrative, phenomenology, grounded theory, ethnography, and case studies. The narrative approach describes the lives of individuals or groups under study, with the research results described narratively and chronologically.

The approach in this study refers to the researcher's efforts to establish a relationship with the object under study (Nawawi & Hadari, 1995). Although the research problem can be the same, researchers can often choose between two or more approaches to solving the problem. The historical approach, for example, invites researchers to enter the context of an event or occurrence. This study is used to understand the phenomenon in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition that is still maintained today. The anthropological approach analyzes value systems, arts, culture, and customary history in the Polewali Mandar Regency. In contrast, the religious approach looks at how community religiosity is influenced by religious orthodoxy and rituals and Islamic cultural values in the local community.

The data sources used in this study are divided into two categories, namely primary data and secondary data. Primary data is obtained directly from informants (Sugiyono., 2012), such as traditional leaders and community leaders in Karama Village, Tinambung District, and Polewali Mandar Regency. Secondary data sources are obtained indirectly, through literature, archives, or documents relevant to the research focus.

Several methods were used to collect data, including observation, interviews, photovoice, and documentation. Observations were conducted to obtain information about human behavior in the study context. The interviews conducted were unstructured interviews, which are more flexible and in-depth, allowing the researcher to understand the real situation in the field (Moleong, 2001). Photovoice was used to engage participants in an in-depth process with their community through drawings or photographs. In contrast, documentation was used to obtain data from books, archives, or documents related to the research.

The main instrument in qualitative research is the researcher, who functions as an instrument to determine the focus of research, select informants, collect data, and conduct analysis. Some other supporting instruments include observation guidelines used in the observation process, interview guidelines containing a list of questions for interviews, and documentation formats used to record data in the form of relevant documents or archives (Sugiyono., 2017).

Data analysis has three main stages: data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing. Data reduction involves simplifying the rough data obtained by organizing and categorizing information. Data presentation is done by compiling the reduced data in a descriptive narrative form, to facilitate understanding and decision making (Junaid, 2016). Concluding is done with an inductive pattern: drawing specific conclusions based on general statements.

To test the validity of the data, this study uses triangulation techniques, namely checking data from various sources and using multiple data collection techniques. Triangulation helps ensure that the data obtained is valid and reliable (Sugiyono., 2017), by Combining different sources and procedures in this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Forms of Islamic Cultural Acculturation in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq Tradition in Karama Village

1. History and origins of the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition

Talking about history cannot be separated from the role of ancestors in the past as the leading actors in the birth of a culture or tradition that creates a new order in life. The Mandar tribe is famous for its exceptionally diverse cultures or traditions. The culture or tradition that is very well known in Mandar land is the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition, especially in the Polewali Mandar area, Tinambung sub-district, Karama Village.

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The Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition in Tinambung District, Polewali Mandar Regency, is a form of gratitude to Allah SWT for the birth of the Prophet Muhammad SAW as a good role model and the last messenger in life. The tradition was not born just like that; there is a history behind the birth of this Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition.

The history of the birth of the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition in Mandar originated from the habit of the Mandar people, even from the King, who made the Horse (Saeyyang) the main transportation for making a trip. In the past, horses were vehicles that were considered luxurious and had prestigious values; even the types of horses owned by someone could classify a person's social strata at that time. The bigger and blacker the horse, the higher the value of the social strata. Departing from this, the traditional process was created. Apart from the habit of Mandar people making Horses their main transportation, another version assumes that the creation of the tradition, due to the clash between religion and culture at that time, was marked by the first entry of Islam in the Balanipa Kingdom.

As explained by As'ad Sattari, after Islam began to enter and develop at the level of the Balanipa community or the Balanipa Kingdom since the 17th century during the reign of Kakanna I Pattang, and at that time, Islam had become the official religion of the Kingdom. As one of the elements of cultural formation, Islam eventually formed a new culture for the people of Balanipa, especially in reading the Qur'an.

Along with the increasing interest in reading the Qur'an of the Karama community due to the influence of the entry of Islam in Karama, this is also the basis for the creation of acculturation between culture and religion as outlined in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition, from here the community leaders and historians think that the beginning of the creation of the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition began since the increasing interest in reading the Qur'an among the Karama community. The Mandar people, especially Karama, believe that completing the Qur'an, which is outlined in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition, has a very close relationship with one another, because this tradition is held to appreciate children who have finished reading the Qur'an.

The high appreciation is in the form of riding a trained horse accompanied by the sound of tambourines and strings of kalinda'da (Mandar poetry), which contains praise to the pessawe (the girl who is in front accompanying the child who is khatam Al-Qur'an), which is carried out with the entry of the maulid month as a form of gratitude for the birth of the prophet Muhammad SAW. This tradition is based on the community's traditional or hereditary beliefs. Tradition is a way of thinking of human groups, which functions to reinforce the current order, or in other words, to reinforce concepts and ideas that particular communities have adopted.

The Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition began after Islam became the official religion of several kingdoms in Mandar. Initially, it was only developed among the royal family (mara'dia), but now it has developed to all levels of society. Islam began to enter and establish in the Balanipa community or Balanipa kingdom since the 17th century during the reign of the 4th Balanipa king, Daetta Tommuane. At that time, Islam had become the official religion of the kingdom.

The results of research on the origin of the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition, in this case as stated by Ahmad Ma'Danrang as the Village Head in Karama Village during the interview, stated that:

"Saeyyang Pattuqduq began to exist during the reign of the Balanipa Kingdom in Mandar. At that time, Mara'dia paraded his son around the village using his horse because horses were the most luxurious vehicles. After that, he announced to his people that children who had completed the Qur'an would be paraded around the village using Mara'dia's horse. The people were very enthusiastic about Mara'dia's statement, then told their children to immediately khatam al-Qur'an. This tradition is carried out from generation to generation, so it has become a culture in Mandar".¹

In addition, as stated by Ridwan Alimuddin, a Karama Village culturist, stated that:

"When Mara'dia (King) Balanipa, his consort, and his daughter rode his horse, which danced when it heard its stable being hit and now used a tambourine, while the horse danced, the king chanted kalinda'da (Mandar Pantun). After that, the king told his daughter, "learn to recite the Koran, son.

¹ Ahmad Ma'Danrang, Karama Village Head, interview, Polewali Mandar Regency, June 20, 2024.

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If you finish the Koran, I will put you on the Pattuqduq horse and take you around the village". Then the king fulfilled the promise when his daughter finished the Koran".²

So, based on the interview above, the beginning of this tradition emerged as a form of appreciation from the king of Balanipa to children who, at that time, had finished the Qur'an, by being paraded around the village using a horse that was good at dancing or Saeyyang Pattuqduq. At that time, in Mandar, horses were used as the most luxurious vehicles and were considered jewelry.

In terms of horses, it has been explained in the Qur'an, Allah Swt says in Q.S an-Nahl/16: 8:

وَالْحَيْلَ وَالْبَعَالَ وَالْحَمِيرَ لِتَرْكَبُوهَا وَزِينَةً وَيَخْلُقُ مَا لَا تَعْلَمُونَ

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8. (He has created) horses, mules,412) and donkeys for you to ride, so they are ornaments. Allah has created what you do not know. 412) A mule is a combination of a horse and a donkey (Ministry of Religious Affairs, 2015).

The verse describes the function of horses and donkeys as mounts and ornaments, without referring to them as means of transportation like livestock. Whoever looks at the rugged and strong horses, or other animals, then his heart will be amazed because of its beauty, so the horse is not only a means of transportation and decoration, but Allah created what you did not know at all until the creation you see and know, but if you want to think and direct all the potential that exists then you will know it (Yunus, 2022).

The above verse is relevant to implementing the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition because Surah an-Nahl verse 8 explains that horses are essential in implementing this tradition. Horses, as in the verse above as mounts and jewelry, while in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition in Mandar, people use horses as motivation for a child to immediately khatam al-Qur'an and the child is paraded around the village riding a dancing horse commonly called Saeyyang Pattuqduq, horses are also considered the most luxurious jewelry or vehicle at that time.

In its development after Islam became the official religion in Mandar, initially, this Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition was only carried out among the king's family, referred to as nobles or mara'dia in the Balanipa Kingdom, but along with its development, until now, all levels of society can carry out the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition, not only from the nobility but also ordinary people can also carry out this tradition.

Every child in Karama Village who has completed the Qur'an will be given an award or gift, namely to be paraded around the village using a horse, because in Mandar in ancient times it was a very special vehicle, which at that time only the noble group (mara'dia) or the king's family could be paraded around the village using a horse.

Regarding the development of the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition as stated by Mr. Ahmad Asdy as a religious figure in Karama Village, he stated that:

"Imam Karama developed this tradition by raising children who have completed the Koran on a horse, accompanied by a woman considered noble, as a form of appreciation. The form of appreciation will be paraded on a dancing horse called Saeyyang Pattuqduq. At that time, the children will be paraded around the mosque 7 times like the Tawaf around the Kaaba performed by the pilgrims, after which they will be paraded around the village."³

Based on the interview results above, it can be concluded that the development of Saeyyang Pattuqduq began in Karama Village, which Ahmad Asdy brought. At that time, children who had finished the Qur'an were paraded around the village using Saeyyang Pattuqduq or horses good at dancing, starting with circling the mosque 7 times.

However, now the tradition of circling the mosque 7 times is starting to disappear as it is only being paraded around the village. Previously, this tradition did not have to be carried out when

² Ridwan Alimuddin, as a culturist of Karama Village, interview, Polewali Mandar Regency, June 20, 2024.

³ Ahmad Asdy, religious leader in Karama Village, interview, Polewali Mandar Regency, June 20, 2024.

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celebrating the maulid of the Prophet Muhammad PBUH. However, as Islam spread, it was coupled with the celebration of the maulid of the Prophet Muhammad PBUH as a form of fusion or acculturation between Islamic culture and Mandar culture.

2. Elements of local culture in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition

The Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition reflects the richness of the local culture of the Mandar people, which is full of symbolic, aesthetic, and spiritual meanings. One of the most critical elements is the local language used in accompanying songs and traditional narratives. Mandarin is not only a means of communication, but also a means of inheriting traditional values and ethnic identity. Through the local language, Saeyyang Pattuqduq functions as a medium for language preservation, which is now starting to be marginalized by the dominance of national and global languages.

In addition, traditional music and song elements are very prominent in implementing Saeyyang Pattuqduq. The procession is often accompanied by tambourine music and the chanting of kalindaqdaq, a Mandar rhythmic poem sung with great appreciation. Kalindaqdaq serves as an oral expression of good values, hopes, and praise for children who have completed the Qur'an and a form of entertainment rooted in local traditions. The rhythms and verses create a sacred and festive feel that enriches the aesthetics of this tradition.

Elements of local culture are also seen in the traditional clothing worn by the children being paraded and the decorations on the horses. Boys usually wear silk sarongs, traditional suits, and songkok, while girls wear kebaya or baju bodo in bright colors. The horse (Saeyyang), the main icon of this tradition, is also decorated with colorful fabrics, beads, and headdresses that reinforce the symbolism of greatness and glory. These garments not only beautify the procession but also emphasize ethnic identity and pride in cultural heritage.

Another symbolic meaning contained in Saeyyang Pattuqduq is the symbolization of social status and honor. The child who is paraded on an ornamental horse is a child who has completed learning the Qur'an and, therefore, deserves to be honored and celebrated by the community. This tradition becomes a medium for social recognition of religious achievement, displaying family and community pride in the young generation of knowledge. The honor given reflects the value structure of the Mandar society, which upholds religious and moral education.

The implementation of Saeyyang Pattuqduq is also very strong, with a spirit of cooperation and community participation. The nuclear family is involved, and neighbors, traditional leaders, religious leaders, and the general public prepare the procession, music, food, and secure the procession. This collective participation strengthens social ties within the community and reflects the traditional solidarity values that are still strong in the Mandar people's daily lives. On the other hand, this tradition contains elements of local spirituality and religion that transformed with the introduction of Islam. In the past, Saeyyang Pattuqduq could be associated with elements of animistic beliefs and ancestor spirit worship. However, the practice has now been replaced with the recitation of Islamic prayers and tahlil as a form of gratitude for the child's achievements. Nevertheless, traces of local spirituality remain evident in the use of certain symbols and the community's belief in the sacred value of this procession.

Equally important, Saeyyang Pattuqduq is part of a traditional ritual or ceremony with a social and spiritual function. It is not just an ordinary celebration, but a rite of passage - a transitional rite - that marks children's growth from the learning phase to the phase of public recognition. In this context, Saeyyang Pattuqduq becomes a vehicle for forming the child's identity within the family, religion, and the wider community. The main symbol of this tradition is the horse (Saeyyang), which has high cultural value in Mandar society.

Horses are not just a means of transportation, but a symbol of strength, might, and nobility. The choice of a horse as a child's vehicle in Saeyyang Pattuqduq implies that a child who has learned the Qur'an is a figure who should be exalted and upheld. Horses represent the relationship between humans and nature and animals in local culture.

All of these elements form a complex and rich tradition. Saeyyang Pattuqduq not only presents a cultural performance, but also reflects the value system, social structure, and cultural identity of the Mandar people. The continuation of this tradition is very important to maintain the continuity of

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local culture, which is now facing the challenges of modernization and globalization. Therefore, understanding the elements of local culture in Saeyyang Pattuqduq is an essential foundation in efforts to preserve and revitalize traditional culture in West Sulawesi.

In every organization and educational institution, formal and non-formal, such as the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition, there is an effort to ground Godly and religious values in society.

a. Increased community participation in recitation and congregational prayers.

Ahead of implementing the Saeyyang pattudu tradition of celebrating the maulid of the Prophet Muhammad Saw. They are busy carrying out various activities, such as religious activities, and, of course, they want the community to be able to attend together to study. Based on the results of the interview, Siti Ramlania, as the community, said that:

*“This activity can make people aware of the importance of non-formal education and guidance, both in terms of morals and religious knowledge”.*⁴

As seen from my observations, the community is aware of the existence of this tradition, so they are enthusiastic about following what is being carried out. Every time, the community always takes the time to attend, even amid their busyness with other activities. However, they can attend the activities carried out when they want to approach the implementation of the tradition, which means how crucial religious knowledge is for them, so that they are always present in activities such as learning Maqbarazanji. The community is busy learning the Koran, especially among children.

b. Foster an attitude of volunteerism, mutual help, togetherness, and kinship among community members.

As previously explained, the Saeyyang pattudu’ (dancing horse) tradition has values that make the Polewali Mandar culture very good to be actualized and maintained.

“The Saeyyang pattudu’ tradition can foster an attitude of volunteering, helping, togetherness, and kinship among fellow community members. People willing to do gotong royong will care more about the people around them. They are willing to share and help each other. People can also be more enthusiastic because gotong royong maintains togetherness and kinship between fellow members in the community”.

c. Establish and foster good and harmonious social relations among community members.

A harmonious environment will nourish the community. When one community member is in trouble, other members will quickly help. Good and harmonious social relations like this can be built if people are willing to do cooperative activities.

Gotong royong can foster good social relations in the community, as we can see in the picture.

We can understand that forming a harmonious environment is a platform for prosperity in a better society.

The results of the interview with Ahmad Asdy, a religious figure, said that:

*“Alhamdulillah, with the blessing of Allah swt, we as religious leaders with as much as possible carry out activities when ahead of implementation as a community forum to provide guidance on knowledge and change both in terms of religious knowledge and also community morality, as for social activities in the form of social services and also opening orphanages, and helping to establish TPA to the community to always donate some of their assets as a sense of concern. We see the changes in the community with this tradition, especially in terms of morals and manners in our environment, the community behaving, doing better, and respecting each other”.*⁵

⁴ siti ramlania, as the community of Karama Village, interview, Polewali Mandar Regency, June 20, 2024.

⁵ Ahmad Asdy, religious leader in Karama Village, interview, Polewali Mandar Regency, June 20, 2024.

d. Increase the sense of national unity and integrity.

On a larger scale, gotong royong can increase the sense of national unity, as we can see in the following picture.

The picture shows that every individual in any condition must be willing to actively participate in giving added or positive value to every object, problem, or need of people around their life. This active participation can be in the form of assistance in the form of material, financial, physical, mental, and spiritual labor, skills, contributions of thoughts or constructive advice, or just praying to God.

Based on the results of an interview with Ahmad Ma'Danrang, the head of Karama Village, he said that:

"Communities that are already solid at the RT or RW level will be able to establish greater unity on a national scale. Gotong royong can make people realize that we are all in the same homeland, so the existing attitude of unity and integrity must also be realized from all regions in Polewali Mandar Regency, especially in the Karama Village community".⁶

e. Creating a Sense of Togetherness, Love, and Affection

In this case, the community must love each other between residents, because then the community will feel peace. After all, residents create a sense of always being together in achieving the common good.

Based on the results of the interview, Ahmad Asdy, as a religious figure, said that:

"In the context of implementing this tradition, it is very influential in a sense of togetherness and love because in the context of always gathering the masses, and that's where there is togetherness".⁷

f. Increase work productivity and prevent conflict

Therefore, the contribution of the Saeyyang Pattudu' tradition, which contains the values of togetherness, kinship, volunteering, socialization, and helping. Like helping each other work together and advising each other, so the community can benefit. Karama Village is wise and has a strong social spirit towards the surrounding area and other communities. Strengthening the bond of brotherhood, lightning work, and accelerating the completion of work, including increasing work productivity, can eliminate the gulf of differences, social classes, and society, and prevent conflict.

The Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition of the Mandar tribe is a form of fusion between Islam and Mandar ancestral culture, namely Saeyyang Pattuqduq, which is a form of appreciation for children who have khatam al-Qur'an combined with the commemoration of the Maulid of the Prophet Muhammad SAW. So it cannot be denied that there is acculturation between Islam and the Mandar ancestral culture in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition.

3. The Influence of Islamic Teachings in Changing the Saeyyang Pattuqduq Tradition

The Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition in Mandar society is inseparable from elements of local culture that have been rooted for a long time. However, along with the entry and development of Islamic teachings in Mandar land, these elements transform in meaning, form, and orientation. Islamic teachings do not replace all elements of local culture, but rather adaptively acculturate with existing values, creating harmony between custom and religion.

One of the most obvious elements of local culture is Mandarin in the songs and communication throughout the procession. The teachings of Islam did not abolish the local language, but rather nourished it with the insertion of Islamic values in the lyrics and verses that were chanted. Many kalindaqdaq in Saeyyang Pattuqduq now contain praise to Allah, the Prophet Muhammad, and reminders of the importance of reading and practicing the Qur'an. This shows that Islam strengthens local languages' function as a medium for da'wah and moral education.

⁶ Ahmad Ma'Danrang, Karama Village Head, interview, Polewali Mandar Regency, June 20, 2024.

⁷ Ahmad Asdy, religious leader in Karama Village, interview, Polewali Mandar Regency, June 20, 2024.

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In terms of traditional music and song, Islam has influenced the content of the songs and the atmosphere in which they are performed. Previously, the music and poetry in this tradition could be purely entertainment or even mystical. But now, with the dominance of Islamic values, the musical accompaniment becomes more religious, and some Saeyyang Pattuqduq processions are even preceded or interspersed with recitations of tahlil, dhikr, or sholawat. This transformation shows that Islam provides a more focused spiritual direction, without erasing local artistic expressions.

The traditional clothing worn in Saeyyang Pattuqduq also adapts to the principles of modesty in Islam. Although it still retains elements of local culture such as Mandar silk sarongs, kebaya, and headdresses, now the choice of clothing emphasizes the value of modesty and covering the aurat. The influence of Islam in this element can be seen in the way the community avoids revealing clothing or excessive adornment, replacing it with a more religious and polite look.

As for the symbolization of social status, Islamic teachings reorient the meaning from mere worldly pride to a symbol of spiritual success. The paraded child is not merely celebrated for the family's prestige, but rather as a form of appreciation for the efforts to study the holy book. This shows a shift from cultural prestige to respect for religious achievement, which aligns with Islamic principles.

The value of cooperation and community participation in Saeyyang Pattuqduq also aligns with the spirit of *ukhuwah Islamiyah*. Mandar people participate not only as a form of custom but also as a form of good deed, sharing sustenance, and strengthening friendship.

From an Islamic perspective, helping others in religious activities like this is considered rewarding, so the spirit of *gotong royong* survives and is strengthened by religious values. Meanwhile, elements of local spirituality that may have previously come into contact with elements of

animist beliefs have now undergone a process of Islamization. Prayers to ancestral spirits or supernatural powers are replaced with dhikr, prayers of thanksgiving, and reciting Qur'anic verses. However, this transition has not eliminated the sacredness of the procession. On the contrary, sacredness is now derived from Islamic teachings, so Saeyyang Pattuqduq is a cultural expression and medium for religious propagation and commemoration.

The Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition also retains its position as a rite of passage in the local culture. However, its meaning is now more focused on the child's spiritual development. From an Islamic perspective, the procession is a celebration of academic success and a recognition of greater moral and religious responsibility. Children who have completed the Qur'an are considered ready to enter a new phase of life with more religious responsibilities.

The main symbol of the tradition, the ornamental horse (Saeyyang), is also given a new meaning within the framework of Islam. Whereas in the past, the horse was considered to have supernatural powers or to be a symbol of traditional heroism, it is now interpreted as a symbol of the glory given by God to His knowledgeable servants.

In Islam, animals such as horses are also valued as creations of God that have a role in the history of prophethood and jihad. Thus, the presence of horses in Saeyyang Pattuqduq does not contradict Islamic values and can even be seen as an affirmation of noble religious values.

From all these explanations, it appears that the influence of Islamic teachings does not necessarily negate elements of local culture, but rather adjusts them gradually. Islam in Mandar was accepted through a culturally inclusive and respectful approach, resulting in distinctive forms of local Islamic culture, such as Saeyyang Pattuqduq. Islamization proceeded through acculturation, not confrontation, thus creating a harmonious integration between religion and culture.

So that Saeyyang Pattuqduq is an example of how local culture can survive and even become more alive with the influence of Islamic teachings, as long as its core values do not conflict with the principles of *tawhid*, morals, and *sharia*, this tradition is a cultural heritage that is not only visually beautiful and historically rich, but also full of spiritual and educational messages for the younger generation of Mandar Muslims.

4. Islamic Symbols and Meanings in the Implementation of Saeyyang Pattuqduq

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The Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition, although rooted in Mandar local culture, has undergone a deep acculturation process with Islamic teachings. Along with the development of the Mandar society, the majority of which embraced Islam, various elements in this tradition experienced Islamization in terms of symbolism and substance. (A. Haris, 2020) The presence of Islamic values Does not eliminate the richness of local culture, but rather provides a new spiritual framework that enriches the meaning of implementing the tradition. Saeyyang Pattuqduq is now a cultural symbol and a strong medium of religious expression.

a. The Horse as a Symbol of Glory and Majesty in Islam

In this tradition, the horse (Saeyyang) is not just a means of transportation but also has a deep symbolism of majesty, both in Mandar culture and Islamic tradition. In Islamic teachings, the horse is a glorified animal, even mentioned in the Qur'an, as in QS. Al-'Adiyat/100:1-5, which describes horses as strong, loyal, and brave.

وَالْعَدِيدِ صَبْحًا فَالْمُورِي تِ قَدْحًا فَالْمَنْغِيرِ تِ صُبْحًا فَانْرِنَ بِهِ نَقْعًا فَوْسَطِنَ بِهِ جَمْعًا

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1. For the sake of the war horses that gallop breathlessly, 2. that sprinkle sparks (with the stamping of their feet), 3. that attack (suddenly) in the morning, 4. to blow away the dust, 5. Then rush into the midst of the enemy's assembly (Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, 2015).

Thus, using a horse as a vehicle for a child who has completed the Qur'an symbolizes the glory of knowledge and spiritual majesty. The child paraded on a beautifully decorated horse is symbolically positioned as a person Allah elevates because he has learned the Book.

b. Religious Dress and Appearance

The choice of clothing in Saeyyang Pattuqduq also reflects the influence of Islamic values. Children who are paraded usually wear neat and closed clothes, according to the principles of modesty and covering the aurat in Islam. Boys wear a typical Mandar songkok and sarong, while girls wear a long kebaya or baju bodo with an additional jilbab. Bright colors and local motifs are retained as cultural identity, but the design and style of dress are adapted to Islamic norms, reflecting the harmonization between custom and sharia (A. Ahmad., 2018).

c. Arak-Arakan Procession as a Syiar of Islam

The Saeyyang Pattuqduq procession is not only a cultural celebration, but also a public proclamation of Islam. The public witnesses and participates in this procession as a form of respect for the Qur'an and appreciation for the children who have completed their recitation.

This creates a positive and inclusive space for da'wah, where Islamic values are displayed in a festive yet religious atmosphere. This celebration reinforces the understanding that Islam is not just a personal teaching, but also part of the social and cultural life of the community.

d. Recitation of Prayer and Sholawat

In the implementation of Saeyyang Pattuqduq, the reading of prayers and sholawat is an important part that symbolizes the sacredness of the procession. The prayers recited are a form of gratitude to Allah for the child's success in completing the reading of the Qur'an. In some areas, the procession begins with the reading of tahlil or dhikr together, emphasizing that this tradition relies on spiritual values. The chanted Sholawat also creates a religious atmosphere and connects people to the love of the Prophet Muhammad, the main figure in Islamic teachings.

e. The Meaning of Khatam Al-Qur'an as a Spiritual Education Milestone

The core of the Saeyyang Pattuqduq is the celebration of a child's completion of the Qur'an. In Islam, completing the Qur'an's recitation is an academic achievement and an important spiritual event. The child is considered to have gone through an initial faith education process and is ready to assume moral responsibility as a Muslim.

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This tradition is a form of public recognition of the process of Islamic education in the family and community, and motivates other children to follow in the same footsteps.

f. Gotong Royong as a Reflection of Ukhuwah Islamiyah

This activity involves many parties in its implementation, ranging from families to the wider community. This participation is not just a culture of gotong royong, but also reflects ukhuwah Islamiyah, the spirit of togetherness and solidarity of Muslims in strengthening Islamic values through culture (M.Rahman., 2016).

g. Harmony between Adat and Sharia

This tradition reflects the principle of the Mandar people, who uphold the local saying: "Adatna To Mandar, adaqna To Islam" (the Mandar people's customs are Islamic). In this case, Saeyyang Pattuqduq is proof that customs can go hand in hand with sharia, and local values can coexist with Islamic teachings without conflict (Basri, 2014).

CONCLUSION

The form of Islamic acculturation in the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition involves elements of local culture in the form of the use of Mandarese language, music, and traditional clothing influenced by Islam, through an inclusive cultural approach and respect for customs carried out by preachers and ulama in harmonizing local cultural elements with Islamic elements. Islamization is seen through changes in the recitation of prayers, the implementation of rituals, and the orientation of the purpose of activities that were originally magical into thanksgiving rituals based on faith in Allah SWT. Islamic teachings change the orientation of meaning from mere worldly pride to a symbol of spiritual success. The paraded child is not merely celebrated for the family's prestige, but rather as a form of appreciation for the efforts to explore the holy book. This shows a shift from cultural prestige to respect for religious achievement, which aligns with Islamic principles.

IMPLICATIONS

At the end of the discussion of this paper, the author puts forward several research implications which will be taken into consideration by various parties in the aspect of developing the Saeyyang Pattuqduq Tradition, especially in Karama Village, Tinambung District, Polewali Mandar Regency. The implications are as follows:

1. In preserving the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition, the younger generation has an important role in carrying this tradition into the future.

2. It is hoped that the community, especially the village government, will continue to pay attention to and publicize the Saeyyang Pattuqduq tradition because this tradition has become one of the identities of the Mandar tribe in Karama.

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